

College of Pharmacy
Department of Clinical Pharmacy
Title of the course: **Pharmacotherapy I**
Level: **4th Class, 1st Semester**
Credit hours: **Theory 3 hours**

Reference Text:

- 1- Joseph T. DiPiro, Robert L. Pharmacotherapy: A Pathophysiologic Approach. Latest edition.
- 2- Mary Anne koda-kimble (ed.), Applied Therapeutics: The clinical use of drugs. Latest edition.
- 3- Marie A. Chisholm-Burns .Pharmacotherapy Principles & Practice. Latest edition.

Objective:

The course provides students with basic knowledge about pathophysiology, symptoms and aims of treatment. In addition to the basic knowledge on the drug's use, kinetics drug interactions, dose calculations, side effects, treatment algorithms and patient awareness. The diseases of the following topics will be covered: cardiovascular disorders, Respiratory disorders, Gastrointestinal Disorder, and Endocrinologic Disorders.

No	Lecture title	hours
1.	Introduction to the concept of clinical pharmacy	1
2.	Hematologic disorders: Anemia and sickle cell disease.	2
3.	Hypertension.	2
4.	Ischemic heart diseases	2
5.	Heart failure.	2
6.	Peripheral vascular diseases.	1
7.	Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension	2
8.	Asthma.	2
9.	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).	2
10.	Diabetes mellitus & Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) .	2
11.	Peptic ulcer disease.	2
12.	Tuberculosis	1
13.	Infective meningitis	1

14.	Respiratory tract infections	2
15.	GIT infections	1
16.	Gout and hyperuricemia	1
17.	Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and osteoarthritis (OA)	2
18.	Osteoporosis and other metabolic bone disease.	2
19.	Infectious Endocarditis	2
20.	Surgical antibiotic prophylaxis	1
21.	Urinary tract infection (UTI)	1
22.	Pharmacogenetics	2
23.	Superficial Fungal Infections	2
24.	Bone and Joint Infections	2
25.	Sexually Transmitted Diseases	2
26.	Parasitic Diseases	2
27.	Glaucoma	1

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Case study in therapeutics I**

Level: **4th Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours /week : Theory 3

Reference:

1-Soraya Dhillon. pharmacy case studies. Latest edition.

2- Linda J Dodds. Drugs in Use Clinical case studies for pharmacists. Latest edition.

3-Mary Anne koda-kimble (ed.), Applied Therapeutics: The clinical use of drugs. Latest edition.

4-David M. Angaran, Karen L. Whalen. Medication therapy management : a comprehensive approach. Latest edition.

Objective:

During this course, the students will use clinical cases to develop the students' ability to assess patients conditions, determine reasonable treatment alternatives, select appropriate therapy and monitoring parameters, and to justify those choices by utilizing knowledge & skills acquired in therapeutics.

No	Lecture title	hours
1.	Case studies about Hypertension	4
2.	Case studies about Heart Failure	4
3.	Case studies about Stable ischemic heart disease	4
4.	Case studies about Diabetes mellitus	5
5.	Case studies about Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	3
6.	Case studies about Asthma	3
7.	Case studies about Peptic ulcer disease.	2
8.	Case studies about Rheumatoid arthritis	2
9.	Case studies about Osteoporosis	2
10.	Case studies about Osteoarthritis	2
11.	Case studies about Anemia	2
12.	Case studies about Glaucoma	2
13.	Case studies about Superficial Fungal Infections	2
14.	Case studies about Urinary tract infection	2
15.	Case studies about Respiratory tract infections	2
16.	Case studies about Tuberculosis	2
17.	Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs)	2

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College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: ***Clinical Chemistry*** Course number:

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **Theory 3 .Practical 1**

Reference text:

1- Clinical Chemistry & Metabolic Medicine, Crook. Latest edition.

2-Clinical Chemistry, Kaplan. Latest edition.

Objectives: To exhibit knowledge of human body chemistry levels under healthy and abnormal conditions. At the end of the semester the

students should be familiar with the basic and advanced information in clinical laboratory chemistry and how it relates to patient health and care

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Disorders of Carbohydrates metabolism, Hyperglycemia & Diabetes mellitus, Hypoglycemia.	4
2	Disorders of lipid metabolism.	3
3	Liver Function Tests.	4
4	Kidney Function Tests	4
5	Diagnostic enzymology	4
6	Hypothalamus & pituitary endocrinology, disorders of anterior pituitary hormones, disorders of adrenal gland, hypopituitarism.	8
7	Hypothalamus & pituitary endocrinology, disorders of anterior pituitary hormones, disorders of adrenal gland, hypopituitarism.	5
8	Tumor markers.	4
9	Drug interaction with laboratory Tests	2
10	Disorders of calcium metabolism	3
11	Acid- Base Disorders	4

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Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: **Clinical Chemistry** Course number:

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **laboratory 1 .**

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Department of Pharmaceutics

Title of the course: **Industrial Pharmacy** . Course number:

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours: Theory 3 hours Laboratory 1 hour

Reference text:

1-The theory and practice of Industrial Pharmacy by Leon Lachman et al. latest edition.

2-Pharmaceutical dosage form and drug delivery systems by Ansel HC. latest edition.

Objectives:

The course enable technical setup for coordination of standards for formulation of typical dosage forms and the principles needed to learn mass production of different pharmaceutical dosage forms. Also the course enables students to understand new drug development and approval process in addition to the principles and factors that influence design dosage forms.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1.	New Drug Development and Approval Process	7
2.	Dosage Form Design: Pharmaceutical and Formulation Considerations	6
3.	Dosage Form Design: Biopharmaceutical and Pharmacokinetic Considerations	8
4.	Pharmaceutical dosage forms: Tablets; role in therapy; advantages and disadvantages; formulation; properties; evaluation; machines used in tableting; quality control; problems; granulation, and methods of production; excipients, and types of tablets.	10
5.	Tablet coating; principles; properties; equipments; processing; types of coating (sugar and film); quality control, and problems.	4
6.	Capsules: Hard gelatin capsules; materials; production; filling equipments; formulation; special techniques.	3

7.	Soft gelatin capsules: Manufacturing methods; nature of capsule shell and content; processing and control; stability.	2
8.	Micro-encapsulation; core and coating materials; stability; equipments and methodology.	2
9.	Modified (sustained release) dosage forms; theory and concepts; evaluation and testing; formulation.	3

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy Department

of Pharmaceutics

Title of the course: **Practical industrial pharmacy**

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **2**

Reference text: **Lab Manual for Practical Biopharmaceutics Adopted by the Department.**

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction in industrial pharmacy and pre-formulation	2
2	Effervescent granules: Preparation	2
3	Effervescent granules: Evaluation	2
4	Flow properties and rheology of granules	2
5	Tablet dosage form: Preparation and characterization	2
6	Direct compression method for preparation of tablets	2
7	Wet granulation method for preparation of tablets	2
8	Dry granulation method for preparation of tablets	2
9	Evaluation of tablets	2
10	Preparation of children aspirin by wet granulation method	2
11	Sustained release dosage forms: Preparation and characterization	2
12	Coating techniques of tablets	2
13	Capsules dosage form: Preparation	2
14	Capsules dosage form: evaluation	2
15	Parenteral dosage forms	2

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College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology

Title of the course: **Pharmacology III** Course number:

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week: **Theory 3 hours**

Reference text: **Lipincott Pharmacology**. Latest edition.

Objectives

: To introduce the pharmacy students to various drug groups affecting endocrine systems and their use in correcting abnormalities in the endocrine functions.

Moreover the course will cover the drugs used in the management of neoplastic

diseases, bone disorders, obesity and erectile dysfunction. Inflammatory agents and the anti-inflammatory drugs will also be covered during this course.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to CNS pharmacology.	3
2	CNS stimulants.	2
3	Anxiolytic and Hypnotic drugs.	4
4	General and Local Anesthetics.	2
5	Antidepressant drugs.	2
6	Antipsychotic (neuroleptic) drugs.	3
7	Opioid analgesics and antagonists.	3
8	Treatment of neurodegenerative diseases.	4
9	Antiepileptic Drugs.	2
10	Drugs of abuse	3
11	Hormones of the pituitary and thyroid glands.	4
12	Adreno-corticosteroids.	2
13	The gonadal hormones and inhibitors.	3
14	Autacoids and autacoid antagonists	4
15	Drugs used in erectile dysfunction	2

16	Drugs for bone disorders.	2
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College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry

Title of the course: Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry II Course number:

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : Theory 3 Laboratory 1

Reference text: Wilson and Gisvold Textbook of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry; Delgado JN, Remers WA, (Eds.); Latest edition.

Objectives : The course is devoted to the discovery and development of new

agents for treating diseases, and enables translating the drug structural formula into therapeutic effect. Additionally, it focuses on the methods of preparation for some pharmaceutical agents

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Cholinergic agents, cholinergic receptors and their subtypes	1
2	Cholinergic agonists; stereochemistry and structure-activity relationships (SAR); products; cholinesterase inhibitors.	3
3	Cholinergic blocking agent; structure-activity relationships (SAR); Solanaceous alkaloid and analogues; synthetic cholinergic blocking agents and products; ganglionic blocking agents (neuromuscular blocking agents).	3
4	Analgesic agents (SAR of morphine, SAR of meperidine type molecules; SAR of methadone type compounds; N-methylbezomorphans, antagonist type analgesics in benzomorphans). Non-steroidal Antiinflammatory agents.	5
5	Adrenergic agents (Adrenergic neurotransmitters); Adrenergic receptors; Drugs affecting Adrenergic neurotransmission; Sympathomimetic agents; Adrenergic receptor antagonists.	5
6	CNS depressant; Benzodiazepines and related compounds; Barbiturates; CNS depressant with skeletal muscle relaxant properties; Antipsycotics; Anticonvulsants.	5
7	CNS Stimulants	1

8	β -Lactam antibiotics (Penicillins); β -Lactamase inhibitors; Cephalosporins and Monobactams.	5
9	Aminoglycosides and Chloramphenicol; Tetracyclines; Macrolides; Lincomycins and Polypeptides; Antiviral agents (properties of viruses, viral classification, products).	5
10	Sulfonamides (chemistry, nomenclature, mechanism of action, resistance, toxicity, side effects, metabolism, protein binding, distribution and SAR); products; Sulfones.	2
11	Anti-neoplastic agents: Alkylating agents; Antimetabolites; Antibiotics; Plant products; Miscellaneous compounds.	10

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College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry

Title of the course: ***Practical Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry I***

Level: 4th Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours: **1**

Reference text: ***Lab Handbook for Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry Adopted by the Department***

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Preparation of salicylic acid.	2
2	Re-crystallization of salicylic acid	2
3	Synthesis of aspirin.	2
4	Re-crystallization of aspirin.	2
5	Assay of aspirin (known sample).	2
6	Assay of aspirin (unknown sample).	2
7	Preparation of nitrobenzene	2
8	Preparation of aniline	2
9	Preparation of acetanilide.	2
10	Re-crystallization of acetanilide.	2
11	Chlorosulfonation of acetanilide.	2
12	Amination of p-chlorobenzene sulfonyl chloride.	2
13	Hydrolysis of p-chlorobenzene sulfonyl chloride to sulfanilamide.	2

14	Assay of sulfa drugs (known sample).	2
15	Assay of sulfa drugs (unknown sample).	2